

THE SPECIFIC ROLE OF EACH TYPE OF INVESTMENT IN THE ECONOMY OF NEW UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation: this article pays special attention to the fact that economic growth in the country's economy, the organization of production, the stability of the national currency and many other processes directly depend on the amount of investments being made in the country.

Keywords: national economy, domestic investment, investment, investivision project, investivision resources.

One of the basic economic concepts of the market economy is the fact that the concept of investment is widely and quickly introduced into our life today, which shows its essence and importance, its necessity.

Investing comes from the Latin word "Invest", which means "investment". In a broader sense, it refers to long-term investment in industry, agriculture and other sectors both at home and abroad for the purpose of making profits in enslavement.

Today, practitioners view the concept of investment and the investment process from different perspectives. Some scholars still equate investment with the categories of "Capital inflow", "Capital construction". Otherwise, both in terms of investment size and color, now surpasses the mentioned categories. In a market economy, the categories of "Capital inflow", "Capital construction" are components of investment.

In the case of thinking about the economic importance of investment, it should not be forgotten that in this place the concept of investment acts as the initial and fundamental concept according to which there will be a desire to reproduce financial, property and intellectual values.

The enactment of the investment law in Kilingan shows that investment is money spent to produce an economic effect or achieve a positive social result, such as deposits in banks, securities, technology, machine tools, tool equipment and any other wealth of kandaya that can bear fruit.

Based on the analysis of the established legislation on experience and investments of foreign countries, we can conditionally distinguish 3 types of investments.

Figure 1. Types of investment

Each type of investment will have its own role in the economy of New Uzbekistan. Financial investments include monetary units of domestic and foreign countries, deposits in banks, bills of exchange and other securities, as well as wealth equated to them.

Material investments include the main funds, that is, the active and passive parts of the main production funds of buildings, equipment, structures and other types. Аклий инвестициялар микдори жуда ранг-барангдир, яъни улар мулкый ҳуқуқлар шаклидаги инвестициялар ва табиий ресурслардан фойдаланиш шаклидаги инвестициялардан иборат.

The varieties of investments entered into the group of property rights are different from the development of nechoglik in market relations, to the specific sides of national markets. Investments in the form of ACL labor remuneration include author's rights, licenses issued to trademarks, and other types of ownership rights.

Its investments in the form of natural resource use rights extend the rights to use land and other natural resources.

All types of investments, depending on the size of their investment, are the result of some kind of investiture process.

According to the investment participation classification:

A) direct investments-essentially an object anik is a consolidated fund in the event that the implementation of a certain maxad is Real.

B) other investments – these intermediaries are spent on orcali objects, and the received income is taxed between customers.

It is not difficult to understand that the future development of Uzbekistan and the world economy is mainly due to investments, which today almost every specialist and business entity has realized, since the wider involvement of investments in the economy of our republic, in particular foreign investments, has become an important basis for ensuring the effective implementation of economic reforms taking place in

Economic growth in the country's economy, the organization of production, the stability of the national currency and many other processes directly depend on the amount of investments being made in the country. The economic importance of investment is especially evident on the example of developing countries. The importance of investment for the national economy can be seen in the organization and modernization of production.

Investision financing of activities is carried out at the expense of various funds:

Among them are cash and attracted funds, securities issued in accordance with the established procedure, bonds, etc.

Today, the question arises as to what type of foreign investment Uzbekistan should attract more. First of all, we need to master foreign material investment today. This means attracting new technologies and other basic production funds to us. At the expense of attracting this type of foreign investment, the following achievements can be achieved:

- The indicator of the stock deficit increases due to the main production;
- Key production growth increases budget revenue;
- Basic production growth reduces unemployment;

And the satisfaction of the demand of the population for imported goods and services in our foreign Republic is partially achieved by the state in foreign exchange for the import of the most necessary goods. However, in place of this uz, we will reduce our foreign exchange reserves and increase debt.

In its place, if the investiture environment is bad, the investment will flow to neighboring countries. So we have to pay close attention to the investiture environment.

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